

Public Relations Communication Patterns in the Generasi Baru Indonesia/Gen BI: A Case Study at Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study is to describe the PR activities and communication patterns carried out by the PR of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara in communicating the GenBI program before and during the Covid-19 pandemic. The research method used is an instrumental case study. The results showed that the PR activities underwent changes during the covid-19 pandemic. Before the Pandemic the PR disseminated information using face-to-face activities, and had a limited target audience. Meanwhile, during the pandemic, activities are carried out virtually with unlimited audiences. Based on the media used, the communication pattern has not changed due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and the patterns are carried out in combination, namely the primary communication and secondary communication pattern. Meanwhile, if viewed from the communication network that occurs, the communication pattern used is the Y network communication pattern.

Keywords:- Communication Pattern; CSR; GenBI; Public Relations of Bank Indonesia;

I. INTRODUCTION

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) in an agency that plays an important role in building the image of the corporation and one of the key concepts in the science of business and Public Relations (Windsor, 2001). More than that, CSR is actually intended to participate in developing the community in the area around the corporation by establishing CSR using sustainable approaches (sustainability aspects) such as fulfilling Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This also resonates with the importance of the process of delivering information about the existence of CSR owned by the company itself along with its goals and functions to the wider community. Bank Indonesia as an independent state institution on governance in Indonesia is one of the agencies that has a lot of CSRs, and one of them is the Generasi Baru Indonesia or GenBI. GenBI is a community of Bank Indonesia scholarship awardees formed by Bank Indonesia as its CSR. As a CSR from Bank Indonesia, GenBI plays a role as a frontliner, agent of change, and future leader.

The main focus of this research area is on the Public Relations of the Regional Representative Office of Bank Indonesia of East Nusa Tenggara province, with its GenBI program. GenBI is currently located in two commissariat areas. The commissariat area is divided into campus

autonomy that have collaboration with Bank Indonesia, namely the GenBI of Nusa Cendana University Commissariat and the GenBI of Nusa Nipa University Commissariat.

In the process of collecting pre-research information, this research used a mini survey by distributing questionnaires and short interviews. The survey was conducted in July 2021, with the targeting respondents were the people of Kupang City and several members of GenBI. Meanwhile, interviews were conducted with the GenBI committee for the period of 2018 – 2020. Based on the mini survey conducted to 31 respondents in Kupang City, it was found that 96.8% or 30 people knew and/or had heard of GenBI. Meanwhile, there was 3.2% or 1 person out of 31 respondents who did not know and/or had never heard of GenBI. This finding indicates that GenBI is familiar in the surrounding community.

Fig. 1: Pie chart of respondents' knowledge of the existence of the GenBI Program

Source: Authors, 2021

From 31 respondents, the percentage of people who received information from Bank Indonesia's social medias (Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, Youtube) were only 25.8% or as many as eight people, while those who received information about GenBI from the events (webinars, seminars, etc.) held by BI only 12.9% or four people. The highest number came from relatives, acquaintances, seniors, and in lecture, which was 54.8% or as many as 17 people. These findings related to the communication pattern carried out by the Public Relations of Bank Indonesia (Institutional Communication Unit) in the activities carried out with the

public. Because the public is still able to know about GenBI even though it does not come directly from activities carried out by Bank Indonesia. The pattern of communication plays a big role in the benefits obtained by the high knowledge of the community.

Furthermore, on the question regarding what respondents know about GenBI, as many as 100% (all) of the respondents answered correctly and appropriately. In general, all the answers given by respondents can be interpreted that GenBI is a community of scholarship recipients from Bank Indonesia. This is in accordance with the basic concept of what GenBI is. Based on this data, it can be understood that GenBI as the CSR program from the Regional Representative Office of Bank Indonesia East Nusa Tenggara Province has been widely known by the surrounding community.

Fig. 2: Bar Chart about Sources of Information about the GenBI Program

Source: Authors, 2021

This view is supported by the mini-survey data that describes respondents' perceptions of the role of GenBI. Out of 31 respondents, 29 people answered fairly well the basic points of the role of GenBI, and one person answered "never heard of it", and one person did not give an answer at all. To validate the answers given by these 29 respondents whether they were in accordance with the duties and roles of GenBI, the research provided interviews with two alumni of the GenBI committee of the University of Nusa Cendana commissariat that took responsibility along 2018/2019 - 2019/2020. Based on the results of the interview, it has been confirmed 100% that the respondent's information from the 29 answers is entirely in accordance with the basic duties and roles of GenBI.

In this pre-research, the author also asked questions about the respondents' views regarding the implementation of these duties and roles by GenBI. Based on the data obtained, from 31 respondents, only 30 respondents from 31 respondents gave responses to this question. Out of 30 respondents, all of them answered "Yes" to question.

Since the emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic, there have been many changes in the use of AI. In research conducted by Rita Komala Sari, regarding the benefits of information and communication technology, it has had a

positive impact during the Covid-19 pandemic. The community (office workers, medical, and school children) is greatly facilitated by the use of the internet during the pandemic to go through their every communication process (Komalasari, 2020:48). So this study also looks at how this change affects the communication patterns carried out by the Public Relations of the Regional Representative Office of Bank Indonesia East Nusa Tenggara Province when compared to the previous conditions before the pandemic. Because based on the results of the mini survey conducted by researchers, since the emergence of information related to work from home policy, Bank Indonesia carrying out its activities has always used applications with a digital basis, such as webinars using zoom, and meetings using Google Meet. All face-to-face meetings are limited to participate. And many employees start working part time only.

In the research that conducted by author, organizational culture theory is used to dissect the findings in the field. This theory is used because it is able to discuss organizational culture in which there is behavior from the organization. However, this theory carries a view with three basic assumptions, and this research only focus on communication patterns. The process of analyzing the findings in the field only uses the second assumption of organizational theory. In the physical symbol will be found the behavior carried by the organization in carrying out a communication process. The behavior can consist of habits, rituals, ceremonies, traditions, and so on. Because this study tries to find communication patterns before and during the covid-19 pandemic, the second assumption is very appropriate to look at the habits carried out by the Public Relations of the Regional Representative Office of Bank Indonesia in communicating its CSR program.

Thus, this research conducted to describe the PR activities and the Public Relations Communication Pattern in communicating the GenBI program, with a comparative perspective on conditions before and during the Covid-19 pandemic of The Regional Representative Office of Bank Indonesia of East Nusa Tenggara Province, Indonesia.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

In this research, the paradigm that is used is an interpretive or constructivist paradigm. In this study, the authors use qualitative research. Qualitative research used so that the liberation was carried out descriptively and more deeply. This research uses case study research method. A *case study* is a scientific activity that is carried out intensively, in detail and in depth about a program, event, or activity, either at the individual, group, institutional or organizational level to gain in-depth knowledge about the event. There are three types of case study approaches, namely intrinsic case studies, instrumental case studies, and collective case studies. The type of case study used in this research is an instrumental case study. This type was chosen because this type of case study approach is a single case study approach, with the point of interest or object of research not only in the main case but also to explain the cases that occurred around it and affecting the existence of the main case, in addition, this type is also has the aim of

providing a broader understanding. The title of this research is Public Relations Communication Patterns in the Generasi Baru Indonesia/GenBI Program (A Case Study at Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province). This research was conducted in October 2021. The subjects in this research were divided into three kinds. The first is key informants (the Manager of FK3-Public Relations) of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province and Bank Indonesia Public Relations Staff, then the second subject is as supporting informants namely members of the GenBI of East Nusa Tenggara Province, and the third is one expert informant with a background as a Public Relations lecturer, and an activist in literacy and digital literacy.

In this research, the object of research is public relations activities and communication patterns carried out by the Public Relations (Institutional Communication Unit) of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province in communicating the Corporate Social Responsibility of the GenBI program.

Sources of data in this study came from primary data and secondary data research. While the data collection techniques used in this study consisted of focus group discussion, in-depth interviews, participatory observation, documentation, and conclusion. The technique of testing the validity of the data is used source triangulation. Source triangulation was carried out by comparing research data from three categories of informants, namely key informants, supporting informants, and expert informant.

III. RESULTS

A. Public Relations Activities of Bank Indonesia Regional Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province in promoting the GenBI Program

Findings of the research can be illustrated in the comparison table below.

No	Before the Pandemic	During the Pandemic
1	Public Relations Activities of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province	
	Press releases, press conferences, traveling specials, seminars, socialization, CFD, National LC, etc..	Press release, webinars, LC National Online, BI Fast Yar 2021, CBP, Virtual Exhibition, etc..
2	Public Relations Media of Communication of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province	
	TVRI, AFB TV, SKFM, RRI, Newspapers, WhatsApp, Social Media GenBI NTT.	TVRI, AFB TV, SKFM, RRI, Newspapers, Social Media GenBI NTT, Zoom, Google Meet, WhatsApp, Instagram @bank_indonesia_ntt, Youtube Bank Indonesia Kpw NTT, Twitter BI NTT, Facebook page BI NTT, and GenBI NTT.

Source: Authors, 2022

In addition, it was also found that the problems faced during the pandemic and before the COVID-19 pandemic were based on the data above, which can be described using the table below.

Table of Communication Disorders in Communicating Programs

No	Before the Covid-19	Pandemic During the Covid-19 Pandemic
1	facilities and infrastructure for supporting activities, less of social media followers for Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province and the GenBI of East Nusa Tenggara Province	Zoom cameras were turned off during online activities, Google Meet cameras were turned off during activities, facilities and infrastructure supporting activities is inadequate
2	GenBI is defined as the generation of Bank Indonesia	GenBI is defined as the generation of Bank Indonesia
3	The location for the activities is centralized, and participants are limited	Unstable internet network, logging in problem, and participant control in meeting
4	Lack of public interest in the program, busyness of the GenBI members on personal agendas, and the GenBI members are less participative in disseminating information	Lack of sense of belonging , and the GenBI of East Nusa Tenggara Province members are less participative in participating in virtual events
5	Information gap to members of the NTT GenBI (not open), as well as communication between the supervisor and the committee are not open.	

Table 1: Comparison of Activities and Communication Media Before and During the Covid-19

Source: Authors, 2022

B. Communication Patterns in the Communication Process of the GenBI as the CSR Program at the Public Relations Office of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province

In the communication pattern studied, there was no change in communication patterns, and can be described simply by the following figure.

Fig. 3: Picture of Communication Pattern of Public Relations of BI NTT in Communicating GenBI

Source: Authors, 2022

Meanwhile, the findings on the pattern of communication carried out by GenBI can be illustrated with the following pattern.

Fig. 4: Picture of Communication Pattern for GenBI of East Nusa Tenggara Province

Source: Authors, 2022

IV. DISCUSSION

A. *The Public Relations Activities of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province in communicating GenBI*

a) Strategic functions

Bank Indonesia as the Central Bank of the Republic of Indonesia plays a major role in maintaining Indonesia's economic stability, particularly in monetary policy. In addition, it also oversees the role in creating a cadre of future leaders who are ready to bring out change, who will later become the front line in the sustainability of the governance system in Indonesia.

Both before the Covid-19 Pandemic and during the Covid-19 Pandemic, the Public Relations of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province continued to carry out their duties. Substantially, the tasks carried out include the main tasks of Public Relations. Within this main task, there is a Bank Indonesia social program known as the GenBI program. In disseminating information about the GenBI program, the Public Relations has carried out its duties in accordance with its main duties. Hadari Nawawi (1988:74) explains that the main tasks of public relations organizations or institutions include:

- Providing information to the public or parties who need it so that the aims, objectives and activities of the organization are known.
- Assisting leaders in providing information to the public or those who need it
- Assisting leaders in preparing information materials to be conveyed to the community
- Assisting leaders in developing plans and activities related to public services a form of reciprocal communication.

The existence of information is an important part of Bank Indonesia of East Nusa Tenggara Province's Public Relations in establishing relations with the public. Public Relations is in charge of selecting, recognizing, and utilizing information for the benefit of the organization and meeting the needs of its public. The communication process that is carried out is not only external, but also internal. This means that Bank Indonesia of East Nusa Tenggara Province carries out a process of reciprocal communication with the external public to build the institutions through its internal public. In addition to information disseminated to the public, there are activities that are always carried out by the Head of Bank Indonesia of East Nusa Tenggara Province in reviewing the results of the activities that were carried out. Although there is no Communication Audit in Bank Indonesia of East Nusa Tenggara Province, yet the monitoring process is carried out directly by asking about how the progress of the program being implemented. Starting from the number of followers on social media, the traffic of visits to the media, and the traffic of visits to

the content that have been distributed through the media. Oxley (Iriantara, 2010:6) explains that the tasks carried out by public relations consist of:

- Providing advice to management on all internal and external public
- Researching, interpreting and anticipating public attitudes towards the organization
- Being a liaison between management and the public
- Providing periodic reports to management on all matters activities that affect public relations with the organization.

So, the existence of public relations in a company or organization has a strategic role and task, or as known as a communication bridge that connects all publics. Activities that will be carried out by public relations need to choose and use the right communication media. Media will help to conveying a message easily and understandably. Based on the research that has been carried out, there is no change in the activities and tasks carried out as the role of Public Relations in promoting the GenBI program as one of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province's CSR programs. Changes that occur more refer to the communication media that are used. These changes in communication media are based on mass cultural changes that affected by organizational culture. This is not only occur in Bank Indonesia of East Nusa Tenggara Province's Public Relations, but also occurs in the GenBI. Public Relations then conducts communication planning by adjusting the existing communication media to the current conditions.

b) Technical/Practical Functions

In order to support the implementation of their duties and functions, the following activities must be carried out;

- The ability to build and foster mutual understanding between the policies of the leadership of the agency/institution and the internal and external public.
- As a service and providing information or news sources, both from agencies/institutions and from the public.
- Doing documentation of every publication activity and events of important events (special events) within the agency/institution, bail stored (documentation) in the form of print and electronic media.
- Collecting data and information from various sources, especially those relating to the interests of agencies/institutions or public opinion that develops as an effort to write and the need to analyze and develop plans and work programs that will come.

The ability to create Public Relations publications is an outline of the practical role of Public Relations. Bank Indonesia of East Nusa

Tenggara Province's Public Relations in disseminating information about GenBI, did not act alone. Bank Indonesia of East Nusa Tenggara Province's PR often involves GenBI in the process. GenBI is also fostered to be able to create independent activities with its own communication system. Based on the results of the research that has been done, the comparison between activists transmitting information about the GenBI program is also the same, but changes occur in the media used and content adjustments. Although Bank Indonesia of East Nusa Tenggara Province social media existed before the Pandemic, based on participatory observations made by the authors, the media was only used with high intensity during the Pandemic. For example, what happened on Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province's Instagram. The @bank_indonesia_ntt has only started actively seeking followers since 2020.

Pacanowsky & Trujillo argue that culture is a way of life in an organization (culture is a way of living). In the organizational culture, you will find an emotional and psychological that includes the morals, attitudes, and productivity levels of employees or members of an organization. In addition, organizational culture includes all existing symbols (can be actions, routines, conversations, communication patterns, etc.). Based on this view, the authors have conducted research with results in the form of comparisons of communication models before the pandemic and during the Covid-19 pandemic which will be explained using Lasswell's communication model and organizational culture theory, below.

c) Who Element

The source element is *who*, which plays a role in analyzing message control. Simplistic message control can also be interpreted as a communicator of messages sent to the target message or audience (in this case interpreted as public). Based on the results of the research that has been carried out, the authors found that the primary communicator in disseminating the information about the GenBI program as a Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province's CSR Program is Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province's Public Relations, besides that there is also a secondary communicator, namely GenBI itself. Although it is differentiated into primary and secondary levels (hierarchically), the objectives to be achieved are the same. In this element, both before and during the Covid-19 pandemic, there was no change at all.

d) Says What

Says what element is an element that plays a role in analyze message content. In general, the message content in this research is about communicating about the existence of the GenBI program as one of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa

Tenggara Province's CSR programs, so that the message elements are not analyzed from a comparative point of view. However, in the order of packaged activities, there were significant changes as described in the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province's Public Relations activity points. In simple terms the message sent was about the GenBI program.

e) Channel

The *in which channel* element analyzes the media used in the process of disseminating messages from the previous element. Or interpretatively it can be stated that what media is used by Public Relations of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province in the process of distributing messages about the GenBI program. Based on this, there is a significant comparison in the medias used, namely before the Pandemic Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province used TVRI, AFB TV, SKFM, RRI, Newspapers, WhatsApp, and GenBI's Social Media as the communication media. Meanwhile, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the media used were almost the same, but the intensity of the use of new media such as social media was higher than before the Covid-19 pandemic. The medias used to inform about the GenBI program are TVRI, AFB TV, SKFM, RRI, Newspapers, GenBI NTT Social Media, Zoom, Google Meet, WhatsApp, Instagram @bank_indonesia_ntt, Youtube Bank Indonesia Kpw NTT, Twitter BI NTT, BI NTT Facebook page, and GenBI (including the members and its social medias).

f) To Whom

The *to whom* element is an element that analyzes the audience that receiving the message. The audience is the target of a message that is transmitted using a communication medium. Based on the results of research that has been carried out, it was found changes in the quantity of audiences, but the target remains the same, namely the general public. Prior to the Covid-19 pandemic, the message delivery process only took place at a certain point and tended to be exclusive. This affects the dissemination of information that is not optimal. Optimization of new media during the Covid-19 pandemic then brought changes to an increasing number of audiences. The nature of the internet that is not limited by space and time makes the media integrated with it and able to gather many participants all at once.

g) Elements of Effect

The last element of this communication model is, *with what effect*, the element that analyzes the effect of the message on the audience. In general, message effects are divided into two, namely the effect on changes in cognition, and the effect on behavior change. Based on the results of the research, there was no change in the effect on the communication process carried out by Public Relations of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province in

communicating the GenBI program. Both before and during the Covid-19 pandemic. The expected effect of Public Relations of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province is the reduction of public awareness of the existence of GenBI as a form of BI's concern for *people, economy, and environment*. In particular, Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province also educates students to be able to take part in being part of the GenBI program.

h) Disturbance (noise)

The existence of a public relations unit in a government-owned agency is a functional and operational obligation of the institution, with the aim of making efforts to expand the dissemination of information related to the activity of the institution or agency with the ultimate goal of establishing communication with the external public as well as internal public of the company or institution. Quite a lot of media used in the process of distributing information, also forms a gap for communication disturbance that hinder the communication process that occurs.

According to Tubbs and Moss, effective communication is when the communicator is successful in conveying information/messages/intentions/objectives if the stimulus sent is closely related to the stimulus that is interpreted and understood by the communicant or recipient. However, Effendy in 2003 explained that in every communication that is made, nothing is really effective, or in other words there is always interference. In communication science, interference that hinders the effectiveness of the message is called *noise*. DeVito in 2009 stated that *noise* can be interpreted as anything that has the potential to distort the message content, or anything that prevents the recipient of the message from receiving the message sent. According to Wursanto, communication barriers are divided into three factors, namely technical barriers, semantic barriers, and behavioral barriers. While Shannon and Weaver in 1949 divided *noise* into seven, namely physical, semantic, psychological, technical, status, frame of mind, and culture. However, based on the results of research found by the author, there are five disturbances or *noise* that hinders the communication process and have been classified by type as follows.

No	Noise	Prior to the Covid-19	Pandemic During the Covid-19 Pandemic
1	Technical: channel noise occurs in communication media used	by inadequate activity support facilities and infrastructure, lass followers on Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province's and GenBI's social media	Cameras Zoom is turned off during activities, Google Meet Camera is turned off during activities, facilities and infrastructure to support activities are inadequate
2	Semantics: interference with the language used	GenBI is defined as the generation of Bank Indonesia	GenBI is defined as the generation of Bank Indonesia
3	Physical: occurs due to geographic location or damage to the five senses	The location of the event/activities is centralized, and participants are limited	Unstable internet network, logging in problem, and participant is uncontrolable in the online meeting
4	Psychological: disturbances that occur come from individuals	Lack of public interest in the evebt/program, GenBI members are busy with personal agendas, and GenBI members are less participative in disseminating the information about the GenBI Program	the lack of sense of belonging between public relations and supervisors of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province with GenBI member, lack of closeness and intimacy between public relations and supervisor with GenBI, and the members of GenBI are rarely participating in virtual activities
5	Status: disturbances that occur due to differences in social status	Communication of the GenBI's committee and the members are not open, as well as communication between the supervisor and the committee of GenBI.	

Table 2: Disturbances Before and During the Covid-19 Pandemic

Source: Authors, 2022

Based on the description above, a comparison of communication activities using the Lasswell communication model can be visualized using the following illustration.

Fig. 5: Comparison of Communication Activities with Lasswell's Model

Source: Authors, 2022

B. Communication Patterns in the Communication Process of the GenBI Program at the Public Relations of the Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province

The communication patterns in disseminating the information about the GenBI program are divided into two, namely the pattern of primary communication and secondary communication patterns. The classification of this pattern is based on the media used in the process of communicating information on the GenBI program. The pattern determination process is based on the dominance of the media used in the communication process (Onong Effendy: 1998), as well as adjustments made based on policy implementation activities due to the current conditions faced by Bank Indonesia. Thus, the communication pattern used by Public Relations of Bank Indonesia in communicating GenBI is as follows.

a) Primary Communication

Primary communication patterns are defined as a communication process that involves symbols in the process of sending messages. The symbols used can be verbal or nonverbal symbols. Verbal symbols can be in the form of spoken language that are used, while non-verbal symbols are non-verbal symbols (language) that can be constructed through body parts such as eyes, lips, head, hands, and so on (Sintia, 2013: 3).

This is in line with the activities used by Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province's PR before the COVID-19 pandemic. Before the COVID-19 pandemic to share the information about the GenBI program, the communication process is dominated by face-to-face and direct activities. Such as press releases, press

conferences, traveling specials, seminars, outreach activities, Car Free Day (CFD), Leadership Camp (LC), etc.. The activities carried out are face-to-face or offline activities. However, prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, there were media used in the communication process, such as TV and Local Radio (TVRI, AFB TV, SKFM, and RRI), newspapers and GenBI's social media (though rarely used). The use of media in this communication activity makes the primary pattern that is run not completely primary, but a combination of secondary patterns.

b) Secondary Communication Patterns

Secondary communication patterns describe the communication process that uses a second tool in the process of delivering signs or symbols when communicating. Generally, the secondary communication process occurs because the physical distance between communication actors (far from each other) (Sintia, 2013: 3). Thus, during the COVID-19 pandemic, communication patterns were dominated by secondary patterns due to the high number of media or communication aids used in disseminating the information about the GenBI program as one of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province's CSR programs.

Sinta (2013:3) explains that in the current era, secondary communication is one of the fields for technology breeding to facilitate communication, so that the secondary communication pattern is closely related to the use of media or communication aids and nowadays becomes more efficient, this is in line with what Public Relations of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province in communicating its CSR program. The activities carried out are all online-based, starting from making press releases, webinars, National Online LC, BI Fast Yar 2021, CBP, Virtual Exhibitions, etc.. The media used are not only TV, Radio and Newspapers but GenBI's Social Media (massively), Zoom, Google Meet, Instagram @bank_indonesia_ntt, Youtube Bank Indonesia Kpw NTT, Twitter BI NTT, Facebook page BI NTT, and GenBI (both the social media and the members).

In addition, if viewed from the communication network that operates within Bank Indonesia, the communication patterns implemented by Bank Indonesia in communicating the GenBI program can be classified as follows.

c) Y Communication Pattern

In this structure, the leader is more centralized and clear. The owner of the most information (information center) is at the bottom, and the second leader can be occupied by people at the top of the information center and so on up. The two people at the bottom acted as members who only got information from the information center. In the communication pattern carried out by Public Relations of of Bank Indonesia

Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province in communicating information about the GenBI program, the information center or owner of the most information is Public Relations/supervisor, because of the informations that they received are from the Deputy and from GenBI. The second information center is GenBI, because it gets information from PR and provides feedback. While other communication members only have one source of information. According to Joseph A. Devito (1998) this phenomenon can be categorized as a communication pattern with a Y network structure. In addition, the position of the leader is very clear because it can be seen from the amount of information received and sent to members (Abdullah Masmuh, 2008:56). In this case, the largest number of messages was sent by Public Relations of of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province because it was sent to GenBI and directly to stakeholders, and the second leader was GenBI because GenBI communicated with supervisors (from the PR of BI) and stakeholders.

Based on the findings in this study, GenBI in particular also has a pattern of communication within its community. The communication pattern adopted in this community is all channel/star communication pattern. According to Widjaja (2000), the star communication pattern is a communication pattern in which the communication network is spread out in all directions, or in simple terms it can be interpreted that each member is able to communicate without obstacles (Widjaja, 2000: 102). The star communication network pattern is also called the all channel because all members can communicate with one another. However, in this communication pattern, those who are able to communicate with Public Relations/supervisor can only be done by the GenBI's committee.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research on public relations communication pattern in GenBI as the Corporate Social Responsibility Program (Case Study at Bank Indonesia Representative Office of East Nusa Tenggara Province), the following conclusions can be drawn.

- Based on a review of Lasswell's theory of organizational culture and communication elements, the activities carried out by the Public Relations of Bank Indonesia for the East Nusa Tenggara Province in communicating GenBI underwent changes during the covid-19 pandemic. Prior to the Pandemic, Public Relations carried out information using face-to-face activities, and had a limited target audience such as press releases, press conferences, traveling specials, seminars, socialization, CFD, National LC, etc., with the media used generally were TVRI, AFB TV, SKFM, RRI, Newspaper, WhatsApp, and GenBI's Social Media. Meanwhile, during the pandemic, information dissemination activities about the GenBI program were carried out online with as many target audiences as possible. The activities carried out include

press releases, webinars, Online National LC, BI Fast Yar 2021, CBP, Virtual Exhibitions, etc., and the media used were TVRI, AFB TV, SKFM, RRI, Newspapers, GenBI NTT Social Media, Zoom, Google Meet, WhatsApp, Instagram @bank_indonesia_ntt, Youtube Bank Indonesia Kpw NTT, Twitter BI NTT, Facebook page BI NTT, and GenBI NTT.

- Based on the media or tools used, it can be concluded that the communication pattern used by the Public Relations of Bank Indonesia Representative Office of east Nusa Tenggara Province in communicating the GenBI program as one of the CSR programs has not changed due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and the pattern is carried out in combination, namely the primary communication pattern and secondary communication pattern. Meanwhile, if viewed from the communication network that occurs, the communication pattern used is the Y network communication pattern.

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